

Evaluating the food safety and risk assessment evidence-base of polyethylene terephthalate oligomers: Protocol for a systematic evidence map

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About this document

The SEM protocol is to be submitted for peer review and this document is to be considered a structured outline of the protocol. Updates to the protocol will be provided.

1. Background

In Europe, plastic materials for food packaging represent one of the largest end-use markets.¹ In the manufacturing of food contact materials (FCMs), several thousand chemical substances are used, the so-called intentionally added substances (IAS). In addition to IAS, FCMs also contain known and unknown non-intentionally added substances (NIAS). NIAS are usually formed as by-products or degradation products during the production, recycling, use of FCMs, or can be attributed to impurities in the starting materials used.²⁻⁶ The manufacturer of FCMs has the obligation to ensure the safety of these NIAS in accordance with Article 3 of the Framework Regulation ((EC) No 1935/2004) and Article 19 of the Plastics Regulation ((EU) No 10/2011).^{7,8} However, there is yet no defined risk assessment framework nor guidelines to assess the safety of NIAS, and clear recommendations risk assessment by food safety authorities/regulatory bodies are largely lacking. One group generally treated as NIAS are the oligomers from plastic FCMs, which are defined as substances consisting of a finite number of repeating units and having a molecular weight of less than 1000 Da.⁷ The formation of oligomers is an unavoidable process in the production of plastic FCMs.⁹ The omnipresence of oligomers in plastic FCMs makes these substances of great concern because, as potential migrating chemicals, they could be harmful to consumer health. However, to date, very few *in silico*, *in vitro*, and *in vivo* toxicity data are available for oligomers.

One very commonly used material that comes into contact with food and beverages is the polyester material polyethylene terephthalate (PET). Its oligomers are known to transfer into food, resulting in consumer exposure.¹⁰⁻¹⁵ In the recent years, first efforts have been made to assess the safety of PET or polyester oligomers in general. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has published scientific opinions concluding that no safety concerns are expected at a total migration of oligomers less than 0.05 mg/kg food from the polyester materials polyethylene furanoate (PEF) and a spiroglycol (SPG)-modified PET.^{16,17} Additionally, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission (EC) has published several papers on the analysis, quantification, and evaluation of oligomers from the polyester plastics, including PET.^{2,10,11,18,19} Their study on coffee capsules showed that some capsules exceeded EFSA's proposed total migration value of 0.05 mg/kg that is recommended for PEF and SPG-modified PET polyester polymers. This raises the question of how to judge the elevated migration levels of PET oligomers and if this poses a health risk to consumers. The authors also stress that their findings demonstrate the need for a harmonized risk assessment in order to evaluate oligomers in a meaningful way.¹⁰ In addition to the lack of risk assessment guidance, regulatory actions focused mainly on migration, and thus on the exposure component, resulting in a large knowledge gap in hazard assessment.

In general, PET oligomers can be considered emerging contaminants and data-poor chemicals. Information on PET oligomers for use in regulatory risk assessment is scarce, but it is not clear what the exact nature and the extent of the information available in the literature is. Typical information requirements for chemical risk assessment are: (i) data for use in hazard assessment, incl. physico-chemistry, toxicology, dose-response, and mode of action information; and (ii) data for use in exposure assessment, incl. external exposure data (e.g., sources, routes) and internal exposure data (ADME/toxicokinetics), either measured (e.g., environmental or biomonitoring studies) or modeled (e.g., PBPK modeling). Accordingly, there is a need to identify all existing scientific information that is relevant to the safety evaluation of PET oligomers, as well as corresponding gaps in the science and regulatory evidence-base.

2. Objectives

The overall objective of this SEM is to map the existing hazard and exposure information related to PET oligomers derived from PET in food contact application, to support future chemical risk assessment activities.

Specific objectives are the following:

- Identify and map the available hazard and exposure literature for prioritized PET oligomers, single molecules or mixtures, on effects measured in humans, animals, ex vivo, in vitro, or in silico models.
- Identify and map areas of uncertainty and knowledge gaps in the hazard and exposure evidence-base for prioritized PET oligomers.
- Make recommendations for future research and risk assessment activities, and policy actions.
- Publish results of the SEM and related recommendations.

3. Planning

This protocol was prepared using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guideline according to the methodology for systematic evidence maps.²⁰ In case of updates to the search strategies or changes to the protocol, the changes will be noted as modifications to the registered protocol in the final publication. As part of planning, a rapid scoping exercise was conducted to inform the whole problem formulation stage, and the further development of the SEM protocol. The intended work will cover the various steps of the SEM process as summarized in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Overview of the planned SEM process.

3.1 Scoping exercise

Scoping is part of problem formulation, which can be defined as “a systematic approach that identifies all factors critical to a specific risk assessment and considers the purpose of the assessment, scope and depth of the necessary analysis, analytical approach, available resources and outcomes, and overall risk management goal”.²¹ Scoping is therefore pivotal in SEM and systematic reviews for prioritizing the type of information required for use in a hazard/risk assessment context, e.g., in deciding which theoretical elements to include *a priori* to answer the question(s) of interest, and how this knowledge will be used in the overall assessment.²² To this end, a targeted strategy is developed and implemented stepwise, combining two approaches: (i) stakeholder engagement; and (ii) exploration of a food contact chemical (FCC) database (unpublished version).²³

3.2 Consultation process

Input is collected through consultation with a multidisciplinary pool of experts from academia, industry, regulatory authorities, research organizations, and non-governmental non-profit organizations. The output of the consultation process will help us to identify relevant regulatory risk assessment activities, technical documents, and key scientific publications on PET oligomers that will be used as seed references for further orientation and prioritization purposes; facilitate the identification and prioritization of the PET oligomers of interest, as well as specific information requirements for the safety evaluation of PET oligomers.

3.3 FCC database

An FCC database will be searched to support the identification and prioritization of PET oligomers in this SEM. A hierarchical overview and PET oligomer candidates that potentially can be identified from literature are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2. Overview on potentially identified PET oligomers and candidates to be prioritized for this SEM.

4. Information sources

4.1 Bibliographic databases

Relevant indexed scientific literature will be identified by searching in the following bibliographic databases:

- Embase
- Ovid MEDLINE
- Web of Science Core Collection (WoS)

4.2 Chemical literature databases

Relevant chemical literature will be identified by search the following chemical databases:

- SciFinder-n
- Reaxys

4.3 Gray literature

Relevant gray literature documents will be identified from vetted (non-) government scientific or regulatory organizations that have covered the topic of PET oligomers in a food safety and/or hazard/risk assessment context. Such regulatory toxicology-relevant technical reports include e.g., human health risk assessments, scientific opinions, position statements, white papers, unpublished governmental research. The list of prioritized online regulatory toxicology databases is the following:

International level

- OECD, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, <http://www.oecd.org/>
- Codex, Joint Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) Codex Alimentarius, <http://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/en/>
- INCHEM, Chemical Safety Information from Intergovernmental Organizations database, International Programme on Chemical Safety, <http://www.inchem.org>
- JECFA, Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives, <http://www.fao.org/food/food-safety-quality/scientific-advice/jecfa/en/>

Regional level - Europe

- European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/index_en
- JRC, Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en>
- ECHA, European Chemicals Agency, <http://www.echa.europa.eu>
- EFSA, European Food Safety Authority, <http://www.efsa.europa.eu>
- SCCS, Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety, https://ec.europa.eu/health/scientific_committees/sccs_en
- SCHEER, Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks, https://ec.europa.eu/health/scientific_committees/scheer_en

Regional level - U.S.

- NIEHS, National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences, <http://www.niehs.nih.gov>
- FDA, U.S. Food & Drug Administration, <http://www.fda.gov>
- U.S. Science.gov Alliance Interagency, <https://www.science.gov>
- NTP, National Toxicology Program, <https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/>
- PubChem, <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

Regional level - Canada

- Health Canada, <https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada.html>

Regional level - Australasia

- New Zealand Food Safety, <https://www.mpi.govt.nz/nzfoodsafety/>
- Australia Food Safety, <http://www.foodstandards.gov.au>

National level - European Member States

- BfR, German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, <http://bfr.bund.de>
- Anses, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety, <http://www.anses.fr>
- UK Food Safety, <http://www.food.gov.uk>
- Danish Environment & Food Ministry, <https://en.mfvm.dk/>
- NVWA, Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority <https://english.nvwa.nl/>
- RIVM, Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, <https://www.rivm.nl/>

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs)

- Food Packaging Forum, <https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/>
- ILSI Europe, <https://ilsi.eu/>

5. Searching and selecting the evidence

5.1 Development and implementation of the search strategy for the bibliographic databases

The search strategy will be developed by an experienced information specialist and the review team. The strategy will be based on the prioritized PET oligomers in accordance with the PECOS statement.

5.2 Development and implementation of the search strategy for chemical literature databases

SciFinder-n and Reaxys are databases designed to support structure-based searches. Both databases allow text searches, but their operation is highly restricted in their applicability of complex and long search strings. For this reason, the literature in SciFinder-n and Reaxys will be identified by structure- and CAS RN-based searches.

5.3 Development and implementation of the search strategy for the gray literature sources

A number of online platforms/databases allow the use of Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT), truncation and synonym search/wildcards (*) or have advanced search engines (e.g., NVWA, BfR, NTP, ECHA, EC, INCHEM, JRC, Codex). On the other hand, other platforms/databases have no search engine option or only very basic query functions to offer that do not support Boolean logic and the use of only single words or CAS RN (all other gray literature sources mentioned in **section 4.3**). Accordingly, the use of search terms and search strings needs to be adapted on a case-by-case basis.

5.4 Citation tracking

To identify possible additional eligible records that were missed by the initial electronic searches, we will screen the cited and citing records of all studies that were finally selected for SEM inclusion (see **section 5.5**). To assemble a deduplicated list of cited and citing literature, we will use the electronic citation indexes citationchaser (<https://estech.shinyapps.io/citationchaser/>), Scopus, and Web of Science.

5.5 Eligibility criteria

Eligibility criteria will be developed according to the PECOS statement (**Table 1**). Studies will be included if they contain information on one or more PET oligomers (chemical stressors), either as single substance or as mixtures. All effects of stressors including health outcomes, kinetics, and biological responses and all study designs will be included.

Table 1. Population, Exposure, Comparator, Outcome, Study type (PECOS) statement.

PECOS statement	Evidence
Population	Human or animals (whole organism), or models that use or target organs, tissues, cell lines, or cellular components.
Exposure	Any type of measured or modelled exposures regardless of timing to PET oligomers (stressors) via the oral route or relevant for the oral route. Single oligomers as well as mixtures will be considered.
Comparator	Humans, animals, organisms, organs, tissues, cell lines, or cellular components exposed to a lower level of PET oligomers than the more highly exposed subjects or treatment groups, vehicle-only treatment, or untreated control group.
Outcome	Any effects or health outcomes, either a toxicological response or a response with the normal biological/physiological range (incl. kinetic information), measured in the exposed human or animals (whole organism), organs, tissues, cell lines, or cellular components.
Study type	Any study type: in chemico, in vitro, in vivo, ex vivo, in silico, mechanistic, or epidemiological (human).

5.6 Study selection

Retrieved references from bibliographic and chemical structure databases will be imported into EndNote 20 (Clarivate Analytics) and deduplicated according to the Bramer method.²⁴ For screening, deduplicated references will be imported into the freely available web-based interface application PICO portal (<https://picoportal.org/>). PICO Portal assists TIAB and full-text screening of literature, and evidence mapping for systematic reviews. In a first step, title and abstract (TIAB) screening will be performed and only studies that meet inclusion criteria elements will be eligible for full text-screening. All other studies will be excluded and the reason of exclusion documented within PICO portal. Studies for which inclusion or exclusion at the stage of TIAB screening cannot be decided, will be included and further assessed in the full-text screening. In a second step, full-text screening will be performed. The reasons for exclusion will be documented within PICO portal. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus.

Gray literature records will be screened at full-text level for inclusion, applying the same eligibility criteria as for the bibliographic sources.

The individual steps of the selection process including the reasons for exclusion will be reported according to the PRISMA statement and graphically illustrated in a PRISMA flowchart.²⁴

6. Coding strategy

Data extraction and coding will be performed on identified full-text studies. The data will be extracted into a MS Access database containing dropdown lists and free-text options. The information in the database will be provided as one or several Excel files (.csv or .xlsx format). The coding strategy will be developed following the study of Pelch et al. and further adapted to this SEM based on James et al.^{25,26}

8. Appraisal

There will be no quality assessment or risk of bias analysis of the studies included in this SEM.

9. Data mapping method

Data visualization of the extracted data will be conducted using various software (e.g. Tableau Software or MS Excel) and the extracted data will be presented in a combination of heat maps, plots, and tables. Each oligomer is listed individually, and the number of studies for each evidence stream and additional study findings are presented in a qualitative overview. The overall information on all PET oligomers, collected in accordance with the coding strategy are divided into tables aligned to the evidence streams and/or additional study findings.

10. Data synthesis

The evidence retrieved of this SEM will be summarized and discussed narratively and prepared as a manuscript for peer review. The data is presented in different formats, depending on the granularity and the objective pursued. Overview graphs such as heat maps or tables will provide information on available knowledge and knowledge gaps. Tables will be used to address research needs and to provide detailed information on each PET oligomer. The information on exposure, health or toxicological outcomes will be discussed for relevance in the chemical risk assessment context. Respective knowledge gaps are demonstrated and research needs addressed to inform future research and policy efforts.

11. Author contributions

Authors will contribute their respective different field of expertise to the development of the protocol. Different fields of expertise are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Review team and the different fields of expertise.

Material and food safety science	Bio-chemistry	Chemistry	Molecular biology	Toxicology	Computational pharmacology and toxicology	Human health risk assessment & regulatory science	Information science	Research synthesis methods
BG	AO	TJS	AO	AO	MS	BJB	CAH	CAH
BJB	BS	VNS	BS	BS		BS		MFW
BS	VNS		VNS	MFW		MFW		NR
JM				NR		NR		
TJS								

The core review team (CAH, NR, VNS) will be involved in all stages of the protocol development, including conceptualization, methodology, validation, visualization, investigation, writing – original draft. CAH will support all activities related to information science. NR supervises the SEM. VNS is the guarantor of the SEM.

AO, BG, BJB, BS, JM, MFW, MS, TJS will be involved in activities, including conceptualization and writing – review & editing throughout the scoping phase and protocol development and in their respective areas of expertise.

References

1. PlasticEurope-Association of Plastics Manufactures. Plastics – the Facts 2020. *PlasticEurope* 1–64 (2020).
2. Tsochatzis, E. D. Food Contact Materials: Migration and Analysis. Challenges and Limitations on Identification and Quantification. *Molecules* **26**, (2021).
3. Geueke, B., Wagner, C. C. & Muncke, J. Food contact substances and chemicals of concern: A comparison of inventories. *Food Addit. Contam. - Part A Chem. Anal. Control. Expo. Risk Assess.* **31**, 1438–1450 (2014).
4. Bauer, A., Jesús, F., Gómez Ramos, M. J., Lozano, A. & Fernández-Alba, A. R. Identification of unexpected chemical contaminants in baby food coming from plastic packaging migration by high resolution accurate mass spectrometry. *Food Chem.* **295**, 274–288 (2019).
5. Franz, R. & Welle, F. Contamination Levels in Recollected PET Bottles from Non-Food Applications and their Impact on the Safety of Recycled PET for Food Contact. *Molecules* **25**, (2020).
6. Horodytska, O., Cabanes, A. & Fullana, A. Non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) in recycled plastics. *Chemosphere* **251**, (2020).
7. Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. (2011).
8. Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC. (2004).
9. Hoppe, M., de Voogt, P. & Franz, R. Identification and quantification of oligomers as potential migrants in plastics food contact materials with a focus in polycondensates - A review. *Trends in Food Science and Technology* vol. 50 118–130 (2016).
10. Alberto Lopes, J., Tsochatzis, E. D., Karasek, L., Hoekstra, E. J. & Emons, H. Analysis of PBT and PET cyclic oligomers in extracts of coffee capsules and food simulants by a HPLC-UV/FLD method. *Food Chem.* **345**, 128739 (2021).
11. Tsochatzis, E. D., Alberto Lopes, J., Dehouck, P., Robouch, P. & Hoekstra, E. Proficiency test on the determination of polyethylene and polybutylene terephthalate cyclic oligomers in a food simulant. *Food Packag. Shelf Life* **23**, 100441 (2020).
12. Hoppe, M., Fornari, R., de Voogt, P. & Franz, R. Migration of oligomers from PET: determination of diffusion coefficients and comparison of experimental versus modelled migration. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2017.1322222> **34**, 1251–1260 (2017).
13. Castle, L., Mayo, A., Crews, C. & Gilbert, J. Migration of Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) Oligomers from PET Plastics into Foods during Microwave and Conventional Cooking and into Bottled Beverages. *J. Food Prot.* **52**, 337–342 (1989).
14. Begley, T. H., Dennison, J. L. & Hollifield, H. C. Migration into food of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) cyclic oligomers from PET microwave susceptor packaging. *Food Addit. Contam.* **7**, 797–803 (1990).
15. Mutsuga, M., Tojima, T., Kawamura, Y. & Tanamoto, K. Survey of formaldehyde, acetaldehyde and oligomers in polyethylene terephthalate food-packaging materials. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652030500157593> **22**, 783–789 (2007).
16. EFSA. Scientific Opinion on the safety assessment of the substance, furan-2, 5-dicarboxylic acid, CAS No 3238-40-2, for use in food contact materials. *EFSA J.* **12**, 1–9 (2014).
17. EFSA. Scientific Opinion on the safety assessment of the substance, 2,4,8,10-tetraoxaspiroundecane-3, 9-diethanol, β3,β3,β9,β9-tetramethyl-, CAS No 1455-42-1, for use in food contact materials. *EFSA J.* **12**, 4–11 (2014).
18. Tsochatzis, E. D. *et al.* Isolation, characterization and structural elucidation of polybutylene terephthalate cyclic oligomers and purity assessment using a 1H qNMR method. *Polymers (Basel)*. **11**, 464 (2019).

19. Tsochatzis, E. D., Alberto Lopes, J., Kappenstein, O., Tietz, T. & Hoekstra, E. J. Quantification of PET cyclic and linear oligomers in teabags by a validated LC-MS method – In silico toxicity assessment and consumer's exposure. *Food Chem.* **317**, 126427 (2020).
20. Moher, D. *et al.* Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015 statement. *Rev. Esp. Nutr. Humana y Diet.* **20**, 148–160 (2016).
21. Solomon, K. R. *et al.* Problem formulation for risk assessment of combined exposures to chemicals and other stressors in humans. *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.* **46**, 835–844 (2016).
22. Roth, N., Sandström, J. & Wilks, M. F. A case study applying pathway-oriented thinking to problem formulation for planning a systematic review. *Environ. Int.* **140**, 105768 (2020).
23. Martin, O. V. *et al.* Protocol for a systematic map of the evidence of migrating and extractable chemicals from food contact articles. (2018) doi:10.5281/ZENODO.2525277.
24. Bramer, W. M., Giustini, D., De Jong, G. B., Holland, L. & Bekhuis, T. De-duplication of database search results for systematic reviews in EndNote. *J. Med. Libr. Assoc.* **104**, 240 (2016).
25. James, K. L., Randall, N. P. & Haddaway, N. R. A methodology for systematic mapping in environmental sciences. *Environ. Evid.* **5**, 1–13 (2016).
26. Pelch, K. E., Reade, A., Wolffe, T. A. M. & Kwiatkowski, C. F. PFAS health effects database: Protocol for a systematic evidence map. *Environ. Int.* **130**, 104851 (2019).